

Evaluation Of Factors Affecting University Brand: Case Studies At Public Universities In Ho Chi Minh City

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 16, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 21, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Brand, image, public school; university and SGU.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5717237</p>	<p><i>The brand is one of the important factors contributing to maintaining, expanding, and developing domestic and foreign markets for organizations in general and universities in specific. The brand image of a university is an essential part of building a position, building a brand identity to ensure that the school's message is well spread. To affirm the role of the organization in general and the university in particular, organizations need to build a strong and complete brand image and brand identity. Therefore, this article aims to provide a conception of the factors affecting the brand and its role for public universities. This research helps public universities understand brands and build a sustainable one. This study identifies the factors affecting the brand image of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. The study surveyed 700 people, including lecturers and students at five public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. There are 650 valid samples collected and processed, including 300 lecturers and 350 students answering 35 questions related to 9 aspects. Data were collected from December 2020 to February 2021. The authors evaluated the scale's reliability and used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to consider the influencing factors. The study has shown that there are eight factors affecting the brand image of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City with a significance level of 0.01.</i></p>

Introduction

A brand is the values of an organization or individual that are tangible or intangible, perceived by those who have experienced it. The brand is not simply a name, a slogan, a symbol. The brand is the perception or recognition of a product or service. There are many different conceptions related to the factors affecting the school brand, such as media promotion (Kania, 2001), training quality of higher education institutions (Thomson, 2002), the attractiveness of several higher education institutions (Utley, 2002), the actual quality of their teaching (Mazzarol, 1998)... Nowadays, universities face competition to attract learners and finding partners is an indispensable step for the university to thrive. The competition in higher education nationally and internationally causes universities to find ways to attract learners through the school's brand. Building a brand image is vital for universities all over the world. Therefore, in Vietnam, universities have begun to pay more attention to build the university's brand image. This article aims to evaluate the factors affecting the university's brand. This research is a basis to help public universities have branding strategies towards the goal of sustainable branding. For that reason, the authors chose to research: Assessing the factors affecting the brand name of some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The university brand is represented by the transaction name of the university, associated with the school's own identity, reputation, and image that aims to make a deep impression on learners, partners, employers, and distinguish with other schools in training activities. In other words, a school's brand is the perception of students, lecturers, school staff, cooperation partners, employers, and the whole society about the values they bring to the community. There are many factors affecting university branding, and many authors have been interested in university branding.

University Brand Factor (BF)

Brand image is the decisive factor and directly influences products and services; brand image is the accumulation of beliefs and attitudes about the brand with many related factors (Bhasin, 2013). Brand image has been studied for a long time; brand images reflect the memory of consumers. The association can come from product characteristics or any related aspect of the product. (Keller, 2013).

A university's brand is also reflected in its reputation, and this factor is related to the image of a higher education institution. Reputation or image includes elements that show the importance of delivering the professional image of the school through fully equipped and modern facilities, equipment, effective service for

students: student learning and research (ToyinSawyer, 2018). The university has logical and recognizable divisions, departments, and faculties—perfect service facilities such as parking, dormitory. Adequate and satisfactory learning facilities affect student satisfaction in terms of service quality, training quality, teaching staff, etc. Sohrabifard, 2015).

University's Reputation Factor (URF)

An organization's reputation is reflected in the overall representation of the brand's past actions and good results. It demonstrates a brand's ability to deliver valuable products to its partners. Brand reputation through the name of the business creates the motivation to attract customers. That reputation is built on the following factors: transparency, clarity, consistent operation, authenticity, integrity in dealing with people inside and outside the organization (Trenatony, 2019). The prestige of a brand is achieved when it brings trust when providing products and services to customers (Tournier, 2017). In addition, an organization's reputation is also reflected by always following the law and demonstrating its legitimacy. Brand information is trusted by the media and communicated honestly. Finally, the brand must create a high trust for users. All these aspects of the brand need to be maintained throughout the development process to build brand credibility (Karris, 2016).

Hypothesis H1: The university's reputation positively affects the brand of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Training Program Factor (TPF)

The university's brand is created by different elements of a training program, including the variety and flexibility of the curriculum and the quality of the curriculum (Abdullah, 2006). In addition, this factor emphasizes the importance of providing a comprehensive and reputable curriculum, flexible structure of majors, and curriculum-related issues to align with university training goals, and student learning goals. The training program has clear objectives, satisfies the requirements of knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Petruzellis, 2016). The higher the quality of the training program, the more graduates will meet the employer's needs, which leads to the satisfaction of the employer and the learners themselves (Raposo, 2018).

Hypothesis H2: The university's training program positively affects the brand name of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

University Culture Factor (UCF)

School culture is a factor that plays a role in creating a university brand. School culture contains typical beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that help create the school's brand (Phillips, 1996). In addition, author Maslowski (1997) talked about the basic norms, values, and cultural artifacts shared by members of the school, events that affect people's activities in environmental education. According to Deal and Peterson (2009), the brand is brought from school culture as a set of standards, values and beliefs, rituals, symbols, and traditions that make up the image of the university. The culture of an organization is formed and developed in parallel with the development of that organization. Respect, cooperation, and sharing are the factors that create the consensus of an organization that creates the strength of an organization (Trigliardi, 2019). The importance of organizational culture comes into play when it helps organizations in general and universities, in particular, to adapt to changes in the external environment (Rellou, 2018). University culture consists of two basic components: material and spiritual. It is the school culture that creates trust among stakeholders and, in this way, creates a brand (Schein, 2004).

Hypothesis H3: University culture positively affects the brand name of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Quality Service Factor (QSF)

Quality of service includes the element of university staff that assist students in fulfilling their research and academic obligations at the university. The university needs to have high support, always do what the school has committed to. All questions and complaints of students are taken care of and appropriately resolved; student information is kept confidential. All the above factors contribute to the establishment of the school brand (Cronin & Taylor, 1992). Service quality includes factors related to issues such as service responsiveness and attitudes of faculty and staff (Parasuraman et al., 1988). In addition, the quality of service is demonstrated through the university's ability to provide complete, timely and accurate information to students. During the learning process, when there is a change in information, the school promptly informs students (Zineldin, 2015). The faculty and staff of the school are always available to answer students' questions. The staff can guide students through the application process, the procedure is complete and easy to understand. The school's staff is attentive during peak hours, and the administrative staff is attentive to all students. This factor

increases the image of the university brand among students (Umbach, 2016). Usually, the service factor has a lot to do with administrative staff's performance of duties (Lee, 2018).

Hypothesis H4: Service quality positively affects the brand of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Effective Operation Factor (EOF)

Operational efficiency is reflected in the quality of training. Currently, there are many different conceptions of the quality of training. The quality of training is assessed by the degree to which the training objectives of a training program have been achieved. The quality of training is the result of the training process reflected in the quality characteristics, personality values, labor values, or professional competencies of graduates that are suitable for the labor market (Al-Khayyat & Elgamal, 2010). The quality of training is assessed as appropriate and meets the requirements of society. The quality of training has two parts. The first one is the trio of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that learners acquire in the training process. The second one is how innovative and adaptive the graduates are (Atiyyah, 2011). The quality of training today is not merely the qualification, the ability to study and practice at the university, which is assessed by the scores of the exams, but more importantly, the employability of graduate students and their ability to effectively use their skills and knowledge in practical activities at university, family, and society.

In addition, applying research results of educators helps to improve the quality of training for schools (Bates & Davis, 2010). The prestige of the university is also reflected in the close alignment between training curriculum and labor market demand. The strong desire of school's leaders and lecturers who always want to improve the quality of training is also the foundation for improving the quality of training the brand of the school (Carter, 2012). The effectiveness of the training is also reflected in the large number of enrolled students, the high rate of graduates, and employability. The school's brand is enhanced if the university is interested in assessing the quality of training aiming to continuously improve the quality, which will build up the school's reputation in terms of training (Dahiya, 2018).

Hypothesis H5: Operational efficiency positively affects the brand of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

University Lecturer Factor (ULF)

Lecturers are human resources that play an important role in creating the university's prestige and student satisfaction. Learners expect teachers to care about not only their performance and academic goals but also their families and understand their specific needs and interests (MacGregor, 2014). In order to bring the brand to the school, teachers need to understand clearly the individual needs and address students' concerns in a timely manner. In addition, this factor is directly related to teachers' duties as academic advisors. The better the teaching methods of the lecturer, the more satisfied the students are with the quality of training services at public universities (Mahi & Kalsom, 2018).

The lecturer factor plays an important role in the learning process of learners. Research by author Gurpreet Kaur shows that lecturers with active teaching methods will effectively impact learners' learning. Through thoughtful planning for teaching and learning; flexible teaching methods that are tailored for different subjects, teachers have a comprehensive and attractive way to convey information. Teachers using optimal teaching methods will increase the positive attitude towards learning and improve the learning quality of learners (Gurpreet Kaur, 2011).

Lecturers are an important factor in establishing the training quality of the school. They are the ones who impart professional knowledge and soft skills. The quality of the teaching staff is a factor that governs the quality of teaching, the quality of graduates and is one of the essential factors for the existence and development of a university (Kasidy, 2018). The outputs of higher education institutions are graduates with bachelor's, master or doctorate degrees entering the labor market (Wetzels, 2018). It can be seen that the professional qualifications, soft skills, attitudes, ethics, and behaviours of graduates are greatly influenced by the teaching staff (Saurand, 2016). Lecturers are evaluated through academic achievements and publications as well as reputation in the field of teaching. Their enthusiasm to share knowledge and experience in addition to their competence are what greatly make up the brand image of the university (Shapiro, 2019).

Hypothesis H6: Lecturers in public universities have a positive influence on the brands of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

University Facilities Factor (UFF)

Many authors argue that university facilities include material and immaterial factors (Shurestha et al., 2011). In addition to the factors belonging to the tangible characteristics, the surrounding environment is

considered distinctive features associated with the organization's cultural aspects. Facilities include teaching equipment, classrooms, libraries, yards, etc., need to fully meet the learning objectives and are convenient for students to study and play as well as participate in extracurricular activities (Pavlou & Fyngson, 2006). Besides, the working environment is one of the leading factors that directly affects the decision of learners when it comes to university selection. University facilities play an important role in the quality of training and significantly influence the success or failure of a university (Negash, 2014). A friendly, green, clean, and beautiful learning and working environment plays a vital role for the departments and individuals in the school to work efficiently, fully reach their potential and collaborate effectively. Therefore, leaders and employees must always focus on creating a professional and engaging working environment; only then will the organisation develop strongly. These factors include the conditions of the organization's facilities and the relationship between employees, colleagues, and leaders (Osakwe, 2014). The organization's facilities such as working space, internet system, traffic, labor protection equipment are the necessary conditions for staff to work safely and achieve excellent results, all of which creates the school's reputation. (Salem, 2017).

Hypothesis H7: The facilities of public universities positively influence the brand of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Student Satisfaction Factor (SSF)

The university's brand brings about stakeholders' satisfaction (students, parents, employers, etc.). Satisfaction is the emotional level of a person derived from comparing the results obtained from consumer products and services of universities with the expectation (Sultan, 2017). The level of satisfaction depends on the difference between the results received and the expectation; if actual results are lower than the expectation, stakeholders will be dissatisfied; if actual results match expectation, stakeholders will be satisfied. If the actual results are higher than the expectation, the stakeholders are happy, which is one of the important factors that creates the university's brand (Parves & Ho, 2010). Stakeholder expectations are formed from actual experiences through learning and interacting with the school. When graduates easily find jobs, the knowledge, skills, and attitudes gained during the time at university are proven to meet the needs of society, which will create a complete satisfaction for learners, thereby creating a reputation for the training quality of the university (Cronin & Taylor, 1994). Student satisfaction with the university's training quality is a comprehensive assessment of educational activities provided by the university (Finch, 2015).

Hypothesis H8: The facilities of public universities positively influence the brand of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

(Source: Researcher discovered)

Figure 1. Research model of factors affecting university brand

METHODS OF RESEARCH

In this paper, the authors use both qualitative and quantitative research methods (figure 2). There are 11 most basic research stages related to the assessment of factors affecting university brand at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City as follows:

Stage 1 (Research title): The project's title is 'Evaluation of factors affecting university brand: Case studies at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City'. This study is usually selected based on the actual situation of universities.

Stage 2 (Research Objectives): The study's objective is to evaluate the factors affecting the university brand in a case study of some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. Based on the experiment, the authors propose recommendations to enhance university branding strategies at several public universities in Ho Chi Minh City (Hair et al., 1998).

Stage 3 (Understanding theories and research related to the study): The author's research theories and works that are related to the factors affecting the university's brand. This stage helps the authors build a model to evaluate the factors affecting the university brand.

Stage 4 (Building a preliminary assessment tool): The authors build a model for assessing university brand factors, a case study at some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Stage 5 (Qualitative Research): The authors built the initial model based on 30 opinions of education experts and designed the questionnaires through the consensus of all experts which includes all factors affecting the university brand, the case study at some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Stage 6 (Adjusting the research model): This stage aims to optimise the model (Hair et al., 1998).

Stage 7 (Preliminary survey): The authors conducted a preliminary survey and assessed the reliability with Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and factor analysis. The preliminary study was conducted on 50 students and 50 lecturers at two public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. This phase helps to improve the survey questionnaire (Hair et al., 1998).

Stage 8 (Quantitative Research n = 650 people): The authors surveyed 650 people, including 300 faculty members and 350 students at five public universities using the survey questionnaires. The specific sample size for each university is about 70 students and 60 lecturers. There were 35 items that needed to be considered. We collected responses from 350 students and 300 lecturers from December 2020 to February 2021.

(Source: Authors proposed)

Figure 2: The process of evaluating the factors affecting the university brand is a case study at some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Stage 9 (Cronbach's alpha evaluation, CFA): The authors used a questionnaire to collect survey opinions and conduct a Cronbach's Alpha reliability assessment. Next, the authors continued with factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor (CFA).

Stage 10 (Official research results): the authors analyzed the factors affecting school brand by the SEM model based on results from phase 9.

Stage 11 (Conclusions and recommendations): the authors analyzed the research results. Strategies are proposed to enhance the brand image of some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The authors have proposed factors affecting university brand at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. A total of 650 people, including 300 lecturers and 350 students from 5 public universities in the City, participated in the survey. Table 1 has 35 surveyed variables, all of which have Cronbach's alpha coefficient ≥ 0.7 indicating acceptable internal consistency. Therefore, the data on the table is suitable and reliable for the next processing step. 35 variables are divided into nine components: (1) University brand factor; (2) A factor of university reputation; (3) The training program factor; (4) University cultural factor; (5) Service quality factor; (6) Performance factor; (7) A factor of teaching staff; (8) Facility factors; (9) Student satisfaction factor.

Table 1
THE SCALE RELIABILITY TESTS FOR FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' EDUCATION ATTITUDES AT PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN HỒ CHÍ MINH

Code	Nội dung	Cronbach's Alpha
Cronbach's Alpha for University Brand Factor (BF)		0.942
BF1	Through the transaction name, the school's logo image	0.916
BF2	Through the media, through the social networks	0.909
BF3	Through Union activities, enrollment counseling	0.913
BF4	Through students attending the school or through the introduction of relatives and friends	0.905
Cronbach's Alpha for University's Reputation Factor (URF)		0.982
URF1	University development vision and strategy is confirmed	0.968
URF2	Build trust and reputation of the university	0.974
URF3	Compliance with the law and legal activities	0.979
Cronbach's Alpha for Training Program Factor (TPF)		0.759
TPF1	The training program has clear training objectives	0.714
TPF2	Training program that meets the labor market	0.719
TPF3	The training program is diverse, flexible and flexible	0.686
TPF4	The program has a mixture of theory and practice	0.689
Cronbach's Alpha for University Culture Factor (UCF)		0.990
UCF1	Clean, healthy, standard environment	0.985
UCF2	All members respect and help each other	0.987
UCF3	There is always innovation and integration	0.988
UCF4	Working in the spirit of cooperation and sharing	0.989
Cronbach's Alpha for Quality Service Factor (QSF)		0.976
QSF1	Friendly and helpful staff	0.961
QSF2	The school always cares and supports students	0.970
QSF3	Provide complete, timely and accurate information to students	0.969
QSF4	The school resolves issues quickly and handles complaints appropriately	0.972
Cronbach's Alpha for Effective Operation Factor (EOF)		0.960
EOF1	The quality of training achieves the set goals	0.945
EOF2	High enrollment rate of students	0.941
EOF3	Student employment rate is high	0.956
EOF4	High graduation rate	0.948
Cronbach's Alpha for University Lecturer Factor (ULF)		0.967
ULF1	Instructors have extensive knowledge, good expertise	0.962
ULF2	Does the instructor use assistive technology?	0.957
ULF3	Instructors are enthusiastic and willing to share knowledge and experience	0.966
ULF4	Teachers always encourage and care about students	0.956
ULF5	Teachers have good teaching methods	0.956
Cronbach's Alpha for University Facilities Factor (UFF)		0.882
UFF1	Good quality of classrooms	0.761
UFF2	Equipment to meet teaching requirements	0.748
UFF3	Full course material	0.970
Cronbach's Alpha for Student Satisfaction Factor (SSF)		0.847
SSF1	Students are satisfied with training activities and training programs	0.806
SSF2	Students are satisfied with the teaching staff	0.810
SSF3	Students are satisfied with the facilities	0.776

SSF4	Provide opportunities for learners to realize their dreams and aspirations	0.828
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The reliability of 35 variables is 0.868. The results of Table 1 relating to the reliability assessment of Cronbach's Alpha of each group of factors show that: (1) The university brand factor has the reliability of Cronbach's Alpha 0.942; (2) Reputation factor of the university has reliability Cronbach's Alpha 0.982; (3) Reliability training program factor Cronbach's Alpha 0.759; (4) The university culture factor has the reliability Cronbach's Alpha 0.990; (5) Reliability service quality factor Cronbach's Alpha 0.976; (6) Performance factor has reliability Cronbach's Alpha 0.960; (7) Cronbach's Alpha 0.967 factor of the teaching staff; (8) Reliability factor of facilities Cronbach's Alpha 0.882; (9) The Factor of student satisfaction has the reliability Cronbach's Alpha 0.847. Thus, most of the factors have quite good reliability (> 0.75). After evaluating the reliability of the scale Cronbach's Alpha, the authors conducted exploratory factor analysis. Table 2 shows the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) of the remaining components in the study, including 35 variables divided into nine groups. The scale shows nine variables showing the factors affecting the university brand in learning. The research team continues to use CFA (Confirmatory Factor Analysis) to confirm the EFA (Exploratory Factor Analysis) results Factor Analysis) is reliable with Factor Loading at ± 0.7 : The observed variables are statistically significant. The observation in Table 2 shows that the coefficients ≥ 0.8 , which means that the observed variables are statistically significant and meet the objectives (Hair et al., 2009).

Table 2
KMO AND BARTLETT'S TESTING FACTORS AFFECTING
STUDENTS' EDUCATION ATTITUDES AT PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN HCMC

Code	Component								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
BF1		0.991							
BF2		0.986							
BF3		0.984							
BF4		0.982							
URF1									0.968
URF2									0.923
URF3									0.961
TPF1							0.940		
TPF2							0.950		
TPF3							0.939		
TPF4							0.851		
UCF1						0.939			
UCF2						0.952			
UCF3						0.942			
UCF4						0.857			
QSF1			0.980						
QSF2			0.961						
QSF3			0.964						
QSF4			0.958						
EOF1				0.948					
EOF2				0.960					
EOF3				0.926					
EOF4				0.944					
ULF1	0.930								
ULF2	0.950								
ULF3	0.909								
ULF4	0.957								
ULF5	0.954								
UFF1								0.946	
UFF2								0.937	

UFF3								0.939	
SSF1					0.958				
SSF2					0.972				
SSF3					0.960				
SSF4					0.878				
(Source: The authors' processing data and SPSS 22.0)									

Table 2 shows the results of EFA exploratory factor analysis, showing that the independent variable is university brand (including BF1 to BF4 with coefficients from 0.982 to 0.991) and 8 dependent variables including: (1) Reputation factor school credit (including URF1 to URF3 with coefficients from 0.923 to 0.968); (2) Training program factor (including TPF1 to TPF4 with coefficients from 0.851 to 0.990); (3) School cultural factors (including UCF1 to UCF4 with coefficients from 0.857 to 0.952); (4) Service quality factor (including QSF1 to QSF4 with coefficients from 0.926 to 0.960); (5) Training efficiency factor (including EOF1 to EOF4 with coefficients from 0.909 to 0.957); (6) The factor of teaching staff (including ULF1 to ULF5 with coefficients from 0.937 to 0.946); (7) Infrastructure factor (including UFF1 to UFF3 with coefficients from 0.654 to 0.972); (7) Factor of learner satisfaction (including SSF1 to SSF4 with coefficients from 0.878 to 0.972). Therefore, the factors proposed in the study have coefficients ≥ 0.5 , which means that the observed variables are statistically significant and meet the set objectives.

FIGURE 3
THE STRUCTURAL MODEL SHOWING THE STRUCTURAL LINKAGE BETWEEN
COMPONENTS

(Source: The authors' processing data and Amos)

FIGURE 3
THE STRUCTURAL MODEL TESTING THE STRUCTURAL LINKAGE

The research model that considers the relationship of variables by the Chi-square method needs to reach the significance level of 0.05, CMIN/df < 5 is acceptable, GFI, TLI, CFI ≥ 0.9 are good. However, in the opinion of recent researchers, the GFI is still acceptable when it is greater than 0.8; RMSEA ≤ 0.08 (Hair et al, 2010).

Figure 3 shows eight factors affecting university brand in public schools in Ho Chi Minh City, in which there are 4 direct factors: operational efficiency factor, student satisfaction, prestige. the school's credibility and the university's cultural factors. 4 factors that indirectly affect the university brand through operational efficiency are: faculty factor, service quality, training program and university's facilities, with significance level of 0.000. Also, we have Chi-square= 2026,403; df= 535; p=000; CMIN/df= 3.788; GFI=0.849; TLI=0.947; CFI=0.953; RMSEA=0.066. Therefore, the research model of factors affecting university brand in public schools in Ho Chi Minh City meets the research objectives well.

Table 3
COEFFICIENTS FROM TESTING STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELLING (SEM)

Relationships of components			Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	C.R.	P	Conclusion
Effective Training Factor (EOF)	←	University Lecturer Factor (ULF)	0.429	.040	10.801	****	H1: Accepted
Effective Training Factor (EOF)	←	Quality Service Factor (QSF)	0.049	0.040	1.248	0.112	H2: Accepted
Effective Training Factor (EOF)	←	Training Program Factor (TPF)	0.069	0.039	1.759	0.079	H3: Accepted
Effective Training Factor (EOF)	←	University Facilities Factor (UFF)	0.191	0.036	5.311	****	H4: Accepted
University Brand Factor (UBF)	←	Effective Training Factor (EOF)	0.139	0.035	3.947	****	H5: Accepted
University Brand Factor (UBF)	←	University Culture Factor (UCF)	0.254	0.037	6.776	****	H6: Accepted
University Brand Factor (UBF)	←	Student Satisfaction Factor (SSF)	0.116	0.037	3.156	0.002	H7: Accepted
University Brand Factor (UBF)	←	University's Reputation Factor (URF)	0.145	0.033	4.474	****	H8: Accepted

Note: **** Significant at 1 percent (All t-tests are one-tailed)
(Source: The researcher's collecting data and SPSS 22.0, Amos)

Observing the results obtained in Table 3 shows that:

- Factors that indirectly affect the university's brand through the school's performance

Hypothesis H1 is accepted: the faculty factor significantly affects the performance of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City is 0.429 or 42.9%. Through the research results, the content of lecturers has extensive knowledge, and good expertise (ULF1), enthusiastic and willing to share knowledge and experiences (ULF3), and encouraging and caring lecturers (ULF4) are the most influential on university branding at public universities in Hochiminh City. (Ho Chi Minh city)

Hypothesis H2 is accepted: the service quality factor that significantly affects the performance of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City is 0.049, or 4.9%. Through the research results, the content of the staff is enthusiastic and friendly (QSF1); The school's care and support for students (QSF2) is the most influential university brand in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H3 is accepted: the training program factor significantly affects the performance of public universities in Ho Chi Minh City is 0.069 or 6.9%. In addition, research results show that the training program's content meets the labor market (TPF2); The diverse, flexible training program (TPF3) is the most influential university brand among public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H4 is accepted: the factor of infrastructure significantly affects university brand at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City is 0.191 or 19.1%. Research results show that the content of the classroom is of good quality (TFF1); Equipment to meet teaching requirements (TFF2); Full Subject Document (TFF3) is the most influential university brand in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

- Factors that directly affect university brand

Hypothesis H5 is accepted: the performance factor that significantly affects the university brand at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City is 0.139 or 13.9%. Through the obtained research results, the content

of the student enrollment rate is high (EOF2); the High student employment rate (EOF3) is the most influential university brand among public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H6 is accepted: the cultural factor of the university has a significant influence on the university brand at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City, which is 0.254 or 25.4%. Through the obtained research results, the content of the environment is clean, healthy, and standard (UCF1); All members respect and help each other (UCF2); There is always innovation and integration (UCF3); Working in the spirit of cooperation and sharing (UCF4) is the most influential university brand among public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H7 is accepted: the factor of student satisfaction significantly affects the university brand at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City is 0.116, or 11.6%. Through the obtained research results, students are satisfied with training activities and training programs (SSF1); Providing the opportunity for learners to realize their dreams and aspirations (SSF4) is the most influential university brand at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H8 is accepted: the reputation factor of the university significantly affects the university brand at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City is 0.145 or 14.5%. The research results show that the content builds trust and prestige about the university (URF2); The school follows the law, and legal activities (URF3) are the most influential on university branding at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

CONCLUSIONS AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Conclusion

The article has analyzed the research works, formed the basic theory of the factors that directly and indirectly affect the university brand, such as: (1) The university reputation factor; (2) Elements of the training program; (3) The university cultural factor; (4) Service quality factor; (5) Operational efficiency factor; (6) The factor of the teaching staff; (7) Facility factors; (8) Factor of student satisfaction to the brand name of a public university in Ho Chi Minh City. The article has applied both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The qualitative research method was carried out through interviews with 30 experts in the field of education. Quantitative analysis was carried out with a sample of 650 people (300 lecturers and 350 students) of 5 public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

The article evaluated the scales using SPSS software to analyze Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and the EFA discovery coefficient. On that basis, a specific scale was determined for eight factors affecting university brands. The article tested the conceptual scale through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), using SPSS and AMOS software. The authors tested the CFA and analyzed the linear structural model SEM to test the proposed research model. Then check the model's fit with the actual data, evaluate the reliability, difference value, convergent value of the scale, and study the impact of these factors on the brands of the public University in Ho Chi Minh City. This result is a scientific basis and a piece of important evidence for the authors to propose recommendations.

The research results show that there are eight factors that directly and indirectly affect the university brand, namely:

+ Factors that directly affect operational efficiency, university culture, student satisfaction about training activities, training reputation of the school. In particular, two factors that greatly influence the University's brand are the University's culture and the University's reputation.

+ Factors that indirectly impact the school's performance are the teaching staff, the quality of services, the training program, and the University's facilities. In particular, two factors that greatly influence the University's brand are the teaching staff and the University's facilities.

Managerial implications

(1) For teaching staff in public universities: Public universities need to improve their teaching staff through fostering academic faculty and building capacity to have extensive knowledge. In addition, to improve the quality of teaching, lecturers use technical means to support enthusiastically and are willing to share knowledge and experiences in learning. Through discussions with students, they expect the lecturer always to encourage and care about the learners in the learning process. In addition, lecturers need to cultivate good teaching methods to inspire students so that they feel passionate about learning so that students will spread the school's training quality to society and increase the university brand.

(2) As for service quality in public universities: building brand image, universities also need to pay special attention to service quality as needed: Warm service staff affectionate and friendly; Always have care and support for students from the school; Provide complete, timely and accurate information to students; Resolve issues quickly and deal with complaints appropriately. The quality of service will make a good impression on people when entering the University, which will lead to the satisfaction of stakeholders and bring brand value to a university.

(3) For training programs in public universities: training programs are considered tools to train human resources for society, so universities need to pay attention to the program. Training with clear training

objectives; Training programs that meet the labor market; The training program is diverse, and flexible; The program blends theory and practice. In addition, universities need to pay attention to the issue that training programs must be developed with the participation of employers to aim at training products to meet the needs of the labor market. Finally, a good training program creates the quality of training that makes the University's brand.

(4) For the facilities of public universities: Public universities need to improve their facilities and the orientations to be noted when building the University's facilities are: Provide a system of classrooms with all necessary equipment for the subjects; There is an entire library and reading room for study and research needs; There are textbooks and references for the whole course; Provide practice rooms with full practice equipment for relevant subjects. In addition, good facilities will help high teaching efficiency to create the school's brand.

(5) Operational efficiency has a great influence on the school's brand. Universities need to pay attention to the quality of training to achieve the set goals at each stage, especially the University's set goals are always based on the needs of the labor market. In addition, operational efficiency is reflected in the high enrollment rate of students; Student employment rate is high; High graduation rate. These ratios are the factors that create the reputation and brand of the University.

(6) College culture affects activities in the University: It is present in individuals' cultural spirit, perception, and behavior in daily work. Universities need to pay attention to building a clean, healthy, and legal environment; All members respect and help each other; There is always innovation and integration; Working in the spirit of cooperation and sharing. University culture will create consensus and solidarity among members at work. Interaction helps school members understand each other better, support and help each other in their work, improve professional knowledge and technical skills. College culture creates the brand for the University.

(7) Public universities need to improve student satisfaction in all training activities. Student satisfaction is one of the factors that positively affect the university brand. To have the right brand image, universities need to have strategic directions such as: providing the best educational products and services offered; Educational products and services should be delivered on time; Provide high-quality training programs. In addition, the University needs to commit to the best academic assistance for learners such as Training programs, facilities, teaching staff, etc. Especially, student satisfaction will be enhanced if studying at school offers opportunities for learners to realize their dreams and aspirations.

(8) The reputation of the public University's brand is enhanced: it is necessary to pay attention to the university information being transmitted reliably, sending a clear message to the stakeholders. College branding needs to create and convey a sense of credibility. The mission and vision statement must be open to all stakeholders and society. Public universities need to make public announcements widely in the mass media through the University's website and notify the University's officials and employees through conferences, meetings, and professional activities. Subjects at the Faculty, Department; Inform students through introductory sessions and academic advisors.

In summary: To strengthen the brand name of public universities, universities need to show good teaching quality, which is the most core value of a university, ensuring the interests of learners must be in the process of teaching, learning, and other activities while students are studying at the school. We need to create a friendly learning environment. In addition, universities need to promote brand promotion and create maximum favorable conditions for candidates and parents to access admission information and strengthen the school's brand through media channels and social networks, always complying with the law and lawful activities to build trust and prestige in the University to society.

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